

Synthesis, Characterisation and CNS Activity of some Novel Piperazine Derivatives

Y. D. KULKARNI, D. SRIVASTAVA, ABHA BISHNOI* and P. R. DUA

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226 007

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Piperazine is a versatile pharmacophore which exhibits a wide variety of CNS activities¹. Clozapine, a piperazine derivative, is being used as antipsychotic agent².

In continuation of our search for novel CNS active agents, we have synthesised 1-(substituted-arylcarbonyl-ethyl)amino-4-substituted-arylpiperazines (3a-l) on Mannich reaction with 1-amino-4-substituted-arylpiperazines (2a-e) (Scheme 1) with different compounds having acetyl group.

Compounds 3a,b,e,f were evaluated for CNS activity and toxicity liability³.

Scheme 1 Reagents (i) NaNO_2/HCl , Zn dust/AcOH and (ii) ArCOCH_3

Results and Discussion

ALD_{50} of the compounds (3a,b,e,f) was found to be high (≥ 1000 mg/kg i.p.) at 1/5 of the ALD_{50} doses. These compounds exhibited no significant gross behavioural effects except compound 3e, which exhibited mild CNS depressant activity. None of these compounds, however, exhibited any significant analgesic, anticonvulsant, antiserpine or anorexigenic activity.

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a JMS D 300 instrument fitted with JMS-2000 data system at 70 eV.

1-Substituted-arylpiperazines (1a-e) and 1-amino-4-

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3a-l*

Compd. no	R	Ar	M.p. °C
3a	H	C_6H_5	110–18
b	H	Aminocoumarin	118–20
c	H	4- OCH_3 - C_6H_4	132–35
d	H	4-Cl- C_6H_4	140–43
e	2- CH_3	C_6H_5	240–45
f	2- CH_3	Aminocoumarin	150–54
g	2- CH_3	4- OCH_3 - C_6H_4	158–60
h	2- CH_3	4-Cl- C_6H_4	132–35
i	4- CH_3	C_6H_5	148–55
j	4- CH_3	Aminocoumarin	270–80
k	4- CH_3	4- OCH_3 - C_6H_4	175–80
l	4- CH_3	4-Cl- C_6H_4	164–67

*All compounds analysed for C, H and N found satisfactory

substituted-arylpiperazines⁵ (2a-e) were synthesised by the known procedures.

1-(Substituted-arylcarbonyl-ethyl)amino-4-substituted-arylpiperazines (3a-l): A mixture of an appropriate aromatic ketone containing COCH_3 group (0.001 mol) and formaldehyde (37%; 0.003 mol) was refluxed in EtOH (25 ml) for 1 h. 1-Amino-4-substituted-arylpiperazine (1 mmol; 2a-e) was added to it and the reaction mixture was further refluxed for 10–12 h. Excess EtOH was then distilled off and the residue crystallised from an appropriate solvent to yield the products (65–85%) (Table I): 3a ν_{max} 3410 (NH), 1720 (C=O), 1210 cm^{-1} (C-N); m/z : 309 (M^+ , 9%), 204 (M^+ - $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}$, 10%), 161 (phenylpiperazine cation, 100%, base peak), 147 (20), 132 (10), 119 (50), 105 (10), 77 (12).

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